

Abdominal Doppler Ultrasonography in Clinical Practice in Cats and Dogs

Çağatay ESİN^{1*}, Murat GÜZEL¹

¹Department of Internal Medicine, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, University of Ondokuz Mayıs, Samsun, Türkiye

cagatay.esin@omu.edu.tr *(Corresponding autor)

ORCID: 0000-0002-7029-9066

muratguzel@omu.edu.tr

ORCID: 0000-0002-8937-5428

Basım/Published: 25.07.2025

How to cite: Esin, Ç and Güzel, M (2025) Abdominal Doppler Ultrasonography in Clinical Practice in Cats and Dogs *VZS, 1(1), 17-30*

Atıf yapmak için: Esin, Ç and Güzel, M (2025) Kedi ve Köpeklerde Klinik Pratikte Abdominal Doppler Ultrasonografi *VZS, 1(1), 17-30*

Abstract: Ultrasonography is an imaging technique based on the determination of echoes from different organs, tissues and surfaces by sending high-frequency sound waves into the body. Doppler ultrasonography is a method for investigating blood flow velocity and characteristics. When ultrasound waves return from moving organs, the rotating waves undergo a frequency change. This change is called 'doppler shift'. The Doppler shift is the difference between the new frequency returned and the original frequency sent. Based on this law of physics, the Doppler ultrasonography method has been developed for the qualitative and quantitative examination of blood flow. Although Doppler ultrasonography is mainly used in echocardiography in feline and canine medicine, abdominal Doppler ultrasonography is a diagnostic method used in the diagnosis of various diseases and pathologies such as portal hypertension, portal vein thrombosis, kidney diseases, pancreatitis, splenic torsion, portosystemic shunts, abdominal tumors, stenosis and thrombosis of abdominal vessels. Abdominal Doppler ultrasonography in cats and dogs can be performed in dorsoventral or laterolateral position depending on the organ to be examined without the need for any sedative agent. Shaving, treating with alcohol and applying gel is sufficient for the examination.

Keywords: Cat, dog, doppler ultrasonography, liver, kidney, spleen

Kedi ve Köpeklerde Klinik Pratikte Abdominal Doppler Ultrasonografi

Özet: Ultrasonografi, vücuda yüksek frekanslı ses dalgaları gönderilerek farklı organlardan, dokulardan ve yüzeylerden gelen yankıların belirlenmesine dayanan bir görüntüleme tekniğidir. Doppler ultrasonografi, kan akış hızını ve özelliklerini incelemek için kullanılan bir yöntemdir. Ultrason dalgaları hareket eden organlardan döndüğünde, dönen dalgalar bir frekans değişimine uğrar. Bu değişime 'doppler kayması' denir. Doppler kayması, döndürülen yeni frekans ile gönderilen orijinal frekans arasındaki farktır. Bu fizik yasasına dayanarak, kan akışının nitel ve nicel incelenmesi için Doppler

ultrasonografi yöntemi geliştirilmiştir. Doppler ultrasonografi esas olarak kedi ve köpek tıbbında ekokardiyografide kullanılmasına rağmen, abdominal Doppler ultrasonografi, portal hipertansiyon, portal ven trombozu, böbrek hastalıkları, pankreatit, dalak torsiyonu, portosistemik şantlar, abdominal tümörler, abdominal damarların stenozu ve trombozu gibi çeşitli hastalıkların ve patolojilerin tanısında kullanılan bir tanı yöntemidir. Kedi ve köpeklerde abdominal Doppler ultrasonografi, herhangi bir sakinleştirici maddeye ihtiyaç duyulmadan, incelenecek organa bağlı olarak dorsoventral veya laterolateral pozisyonda yapılabilir. Tıraş, alkol ve jel uygulaması muayene için yeterlidir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Böbrek, dalak, doppler ultrasonografi, karaciğer, kedi, köpek

INTRODUCTION

Doppler ultrasonography is an ultrasonography method in which blood flow velocity and characteristics are investigated. The Doppler effect was first introduced by the Austrian mathematician Johann Christian Doppler in the early 19th century. This effect is based on the principle of Doppler shift (Maulik, 2023).

Erythrocytes are responsible for a significant part of the scattering of Doppler waves in blood. Blood is considered a heterogeneous medium composed of erythrocytes of different sizes. The average diameter of normal erythrocytes is considerably smaller than the ultrasound wavelength used in Doppler blood flow measurements (Oglat, 2022). Thus, a single ultrasound wavelength will cover an average of 100,000 erythrocytes at the same time. At the receiver, a series of weakly scattered waves will combine to give a total signal. In Doppler ultrasonography, the transmitted ultrasound waves show a type of scattering called "Rayleigh-Tyndall scattering" from the surface of erythrocytes within vascular structures (Bhargava and Bhargava, 2019).

When a sound wave is reflected from an object, the character of the echoes is influenced by many factors such as the amount of frequency difference (ΔF), the blood flow velocity (V_0), the frequency of the sound wave at the time it leaves the source (F_t), the speed of sound through body tissue (c), and the angle of the ultrasonographic sound wave (θ). In Doppler ultrasound identification of blood flow, the transmitter and receiver (probe and crystals) are stationary while the reflectors (erythrocytes in the vessel) are in motion. All these effects are described as the Doppler equation and are expressed in the following equation: $\Delta F = 2 \times F_t \times V_0 \times \cos \theta / c$ (Lamb and Adrian, 2005).

One of the most important considerations in the detection of Doppler shift is that the change in the frequency of the echoes returning to the probe depends on the direction of the ultrasound wave. A maximum Doppler shift is observed when the ultrasound wave is aligned with the flow axis (0°). At an acute angle with respect to the flow, a reduced Doppler shift will be detected (Miranda and Carneiro, 2024). If the ultrasound wave is perpendicular to the flow, there will be no Doppler shift. This is because the blood flow will be neither toward nor away from the probe. The most appropriate incidence angle values to be used in Doppler examinations vary between 30° and 60° (Meola et al., 2021).

Doppler Ultrasonography Types

Continuous Wave Doppler

The ultrasound probe has two sections placed back to back, one producing continuous sound waves and the other detecting returning echoes. In continuous wave doppler, the transmitted frequency is compared with the frequency of the echoes received. It produces a signal depending on the increase (positive doppler shift) or decrease (negative doppler shift) of the echo frequency (Lamb and Adrian, 2005). Since the sound waves are continuous, this method does not have axial resolution, and it is not known where the sound originates. Very high blood flow velocities can be reflected on the screen with this method (Chinh et al., 2021). It is a technique that provides accurate measurement of high-speed blood flow in large arteries such as the aorta, in the heart and in fetal vascularization. (Meyers and Vlachos, 2025).

Pulse Wave Doppler

In this method, doppler information is obtained by sending a sound beam in the form of pulsation. Short-term ultrasound waves are produced at regular intervals, and the echoes are demodulated as they return. (Udeh et al., 2024). The scanned vessel is displayed in a graph called the doppler spectrum, which shows the blood flow velocity or frequency shift. The appearance of the pulse doppler spectrum describes the shape of the blood flow in a blood vessel. The adjustable sample volume in pulse wave doppler allows the collection of doppler shifts from specific locations in the body. Thus, small vessels can be examined individually. This feature is not available in continuous wave doppler (Ambrogio et al., 2022).

In pulsed doppler ultrasonography, blood flow toward the probe is displayed as positive deflections (above the baseline). Flow velocities away from the probe are displayed as negative deflections (below the baseline). The qualitative assessment of blood flow, or how many cells

are moving at a given speed at a given time, is displayed in the spectrum by changing the brightness of the doppler waveform. A faint spectrum indicates a few cells, while an intense, bright spectrum indicates many cells (Bird, 2023). The characteristics of blood flow can also be determined by the doppler spectrum. Laminar blood flow is represented as a narrow band of flow velocities with small differences between the velocities of the cells at a given time during the cardiac cycle. Turbulent blood flow, on the other hand, involves cells moving in many directions and varying velocities as a result of circulating currents. Turbulent flow produces a broad and irregular doppler spectrum in pulsed doppler (Horsma, 2024).

Color Doppler

Color Doppler ultrasonography is an advanced form of Doppler in which the ultrasound device rapidly collects Doppler shifts from many small sample volumes and displays the Doppler shift as a color superimposed on the grayscale image (Maulik, 2023). Color Doppler images provide definitive information about the flow. It is often used in conjunction with pulse Doppler. The average Doppler shift for each sample volume can be color-coded according to direction, velocity, amplitude, and variance (range of velocities within the sample volume) (Meola et al., 2021). In color Doppler imaging, blood moving toward the probe is seen in red, while blood moving away from the probe is seen in blue. Of the other colors, yellow and green indicate turbulent flows (mosaic) (Yan et al., 2023).

Color doppler is one of the most convenient methods to use in veterinary medicine. With this technique, it is easier and less time-consuming to comment on hemodynamic development in restless animals compared to other methods (Samir et al., 2021). The colored display of the flow provides important contributions to the evaluation of the blood supply of the abdominal and pelvic organs and the investigation of tumor vascularization. The distinction between vascular structures and other structures can be made well, and thus more anatomical details regarding the examined structure can be obtained. Since it provides visualization of the entire lumen, any local pathology can be easily detected and structures such as thrombus and arteriosclerotic plaques within the lumen can be visualized. In addition, ulcerative plaques and stenoses can be detected (Bhargava and Bhargava, 2019).

Power Doppler

Power Doppler is a form of color Doppler imaging developed to map the magnitude (strength) of Doppler signals. In this method, the color does not indicate the direction of flow of the Doppler shift. The intensity of the blood flow is evaluated, not its speed. Power Doppler

has a higher frame rate, which increases the signal/noise ratio and sensitivity compared to color Doppler (Singh et al., 2022). Unlike color Doppler, it is less dependent on angle, so it can show flow even at right angles. Power Doppler is a very good technique for assessing the vascularity of organs, as it can show even low flows in small vessels (Fiori et al., 2021).

Doppler Ultrasonography of the Liver

Portal Vein

The portal vein is formed by the union of the splenic, caudal mesenteric, and cranial mesenteric veins. It divides into right and left portal veins that can be observed within the hepatic parenchyma. The intrahepatic branches of the portal vein can be distinguished from adjacent hepatic veins by location, vessel wall appearance, branching pattern, and doppler spectrum (Figure 1) (Derré and Layssol-Lamour, 2022).

Figure 1. Portal veins are distinguished from hepatic veins by the persistent hyperechoic appearance of their vein walls (arrows). With color doppler, portal venous flow toward the probe appears red, while the hepatic veins draining the caudal vena cava appear blue (flow away from the probe) (Lamb and Adrian, 2005).

Normal portal vein flow on Doppler ultrasonography is in the form of continuous low-velocity flow towards the liver (hepatopedal) that may show slight phasic fluctuations (Ercolin et al., 2024). It has been reported that the fluctuations in flow rate are related to the respiratory movement of the diaphragm, with the flow rate increasing during expiration and decreasing during inspiration.

There are some important measurement parameters in the pulse doppler ultrasonography of the portal vein. These parameters change in various diseases of the liver. These values in healthy dogs;

Average portal blood flow = 49.8 ± 13.5 ml/min/kg,

Average portal flow rate = 18.1 ± 7.6 cm/sec, while in healthy cats;

Average portal blood flow = 29 ml/min/kg,

Average portal flow rate = 10 – 18 cm/sec (D'Anjou et al., 2004; Tollefson 2021).

Hepatic Vein

Accurate interpretation of the hepatic vein (HV) waveform detected by pulsed Doppler ultrasonography is clinically valuable because it is greatly influenced by both cardiac and hepatic factors (Percival et al., 2025). The normal HV waveform is tetraphasic, consisting of large antegrade waves (systolic [S] and diastolic [D] waves) and small retrograde waves (atrial systolic [A] and ventricular systolic [V] waves) resulting from changes in the cardiac cycle and right atrial pressure (Figure 2) (Silva et al.,2022).

Figure 2. Pulse Doppler waveform of a normal hepatic vein (Scheinfeld et al., 2009).

Vena Cava Caudalis

The caudal vena cava is formed by the confluence of the right and left iliac veins along the ventral aspect of the seventh lumbar vertebra (Korim et al., 2023). It courses cranially and slightly ventrally along the lumbar vertebral column, in the midline and to the right of the abdominal aorta (Figure 3). Ultrasonographic images of the caudal vena cava can be easily obtained with the patient in the left lateral position. The probe is placed in the right dorsal longitudinal position and angled dorsally to locate the caudal vena cava. After the caudal vena cava appears on the screen, slight longitudinal movements of the probe are made until the vein takes the form of a complete line (Chou et al., 2021).

Figure 3. Ultrasonographic appearance of the caudal vena cava (CVC) of a healthy dog (Darnis et al., 2018)

Pulse Doppler examination of the caudal vena cava shows triphasic waveforms reflecting cardiac activity. The first downward peak represents flow toward the heart during atrial diastole. The second downward peak is caused by ventricular diastole. The third component of the curve is an upward peak and represents a slight reversal away from the heart during atrial systole (Cardillo et al., 2024).

Doppler Ultrasonography of the Spleen

Ultrasound examination of the spleen is usually performed by placing the animal in the dorsal recumbency position. In large and broad-chested dogs, it is appropriate to place the dog in the right lateral position in order to evaluate the craniodorsal end of the spleen. The cranial end of the spleen is located in the left craniodorsal abdomen, immediately caudal to the stomach and adjacent to the body wall. After examination of the cranial end of the spleen, the probe is placed in the long axis of the spleen using a ventral abdominal or left intercostal approach (Figure 4). The hilum and caudal end of the spleen are located (Dominique and Marc-André, 2008).

Figure 4. A: Normal spleen in a 13-year-old dog. A branch of the splenic vein leaves the spleen at the splenic hilum. B: Color Doppler image of a branch of the splenic vein leaving the hilum in a 12-year-old dog. (Dominique and Marc-André, 2008).

Splenic torsion is a rare condition in dogs and cats. It occurs due to hypermotility of the organ as a result of congenital or acquired ligament laxity. It can be seen alone or together with

gastric dilatation volvulus, and the latter condition is encountered more frequently (Beeston et al., 2024). In dogs, Great Danes and German Shepherds are considered predisposed breeds, but any breed can be affected. Ultrasonographic and color doppler ultrasonographic examinations show that the spleen has shifted to the right inguinal region and there is no blood flow (Stillman et al., 2025).

Doppler Ultrasonography of the Kidney

Renal arteries

The renal arteries, located immediately caudal to the cranial mesenteric artery, arise from each lateral surface of the aorta. At the renal hilum, the arteries divide into dorsal and ventral branches. Each of these divides into 2 to 7 interlobar arteries that spread into the renal parenchyma (Sharif et al., 2025).

The dorsal longitudinal position of the paralumbar region is the best angle for Doppler ultrasonographic evaluation of the renal and interlobar arteries (Figure 5). Renal Doppler shows a broad peak in systole with a gradual decrease in flow during diastole (Ito et al., 2024). The flow is continuously progressive. This low resistance waveform reflects low resistance in the renal vascular bed (Moarabi et al., 2022).

Figure 5. Longitudinal (A) and transverse (B) color Doppler ultrasonography of the left kidney in a healthy dog. Vascular flow in the renal, interlobar, and arcuate vessels is observed using color Doppler. AA, arcuate artery; IA, interlobares artery; and RV, renal vein. (Dominique and Marc-André, 2008).

Resistive Index (RI) and Pulsatility Index (PI)

The Resistive Index is a unitless index that can be used to monitor changes in the resistance of the renal parenchyma to perfusion. It is considered an indicator of vascular resistance. The resistive index is 0.56–0.67 in dogs. In cats, it is 0.62 ± 0.04 . A resistance index

greater than 0.70 is considered abnormal in both species (Evangelista et al., 2022; Gupta et al., 2022).

If the vascular resistance of the tissue is increased, the resistive index decreases, and if the vascular resistance decreases, the resistive index increases. The resistive index increases in various conditions such as urinary tract obstruction, acute and chronic renal failure, sedation and anesthesia. In addition, this value can be high in infants younger than 4 months (Evangelista et al., 2022). In their study, Novellas et al. (2008) reported that early clinical diagnosis of developing renal losses is difficult with the help of classical test methods, because serum urea and creatinine levels only increase in the advanced stages of the disease (75% renal function loss). One of the most important early findings in kidney patients is the determination of increased renal arterial resistance and the severity of renal cortical vasoconstriction with Doppler ultrasound (Novellas et al., 2008).

Pulsatility index (PI), like resistive index, is calculated from the analysis of blood flow velocity waves and is considered as an indicator of vascular resistance. Since PI takes into account the average flow throughout a cycle, it is reported to be more sensitive than RI in distinguishing abnormal waveforms (Novellas et al., 2008). In healthy cats and dogs, the pulsatility index should not exceed 1.29 (Evangelista et al., 2022).

Doppler Ultrasonography of the Pancreas

The pancreas is a long and thin organ located along the mesenteric border of the greater curvature of the stomach and the pars descendens of the duodenum. The body of the pancreas can be imaged from the ventral or right side in a dorsal, left or right recumbency, by moving the scanning field caudally to the antrum pyloric and craniomedially to the pars descendens of the duodenum. The vena porta provides important delineation because it is located on the left side and just dorsal to the body of the pancreas. The left lobe of the pancreas is difficult to image, especially in dogs, due to gas in the stomach and colon transversus (Figure 6). A healthy pancreas is homogeneous and isoechoic or slightly hyperechoic to the caudal lobe of the liver (von Stade and Marolf, 2022).

Figure 6. Necrotic pancreatitis in a dog. The pancreas is thickened. There is no vascular flow in the distal part of the pancreas (arrowheads) compared to the proximal part. This area is severely necrotic (Dominique and Marc-André, 2008).

Pancreatitis has various ultrasonographic appearances depending on the severity, duration and extent of inflammation of the pancreas and peripancreatic tissue. In pancreatitis, the pancreas is widely hypoechoic, edematous and the pancreatic ducts are dilated. If pancreatitis is severe, there will be no evidence of vascular flow on color Doppler ultrasonography because necrotic tissue will be present (Gori et al., 2021).

CONCLUSION

Ultrasonography is an imaging technique based on the determination of echoes from different organs, tissues and surfaces by sending high-frequency sound waves into the body. Doppler ultrasonography is a method used to investigate the speed and properties of blood flow. When ultrasound waves return from moving organs, the returning waves undergo a change in frequency. Based on this law of physics, the method of Doppler ultrasonography was developed for the qualitative and quantitative study of blood flow. Although Doppler ultrasonography is mainly used in echocardiography in feline and canine medicine, abdominal Doppler ultrasonography is a diagnostic method used in the diagnosis of various diseases and pathologies such as portal hypertension, portal vein thrombosis, renal diseases, pancreatitis, splenic torsion, portosystemic shunts, abdominal tumors, stenosis and thrombosis of abdominal vessels. With the advancing technology in veterinary medicine in recent years, doppler ultrasonographic examinations can be used to diagnose various diseases early. Therefore, we believe that Doppler ultrasonographic examinations should be included in clinical practice in veterinary medicine, just as in human medicine.

Author Contributions: ÇE: Writing – original draft, Project administration, Conceptualization.

MG:, Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing.

Conflict of Interest Statement: There is no conflict of interest between the authors

REFERENCES

- Ambrogio, S., Ansell, J., Gabriel, E., Aneju, G., Newman, B., Negoita, M., Ramnarine, K.V. (2022). Pulsed wave Doppler measurements of maximum velocity: dependence on sample volume size. *Ultrasound in Medicine & Biology*, 48(1), 68-77.
- Beeston, D., Szladovits, B., & Cortellini, S. (2024). Spherocytosis as an indicator of fragmentation injury in dogs with splenic torsion. *Journal of the American Veterinary Medical Association*, (1), 1-6.
- Bhargava, S., & Bhargava, S.K. (2019). *Textbook of color doppler imaging*. 3rd ed., 13-21p, Jaypee Brothers Medical Publishers London/England.
- Bird, J.D. (2023). *Quantifying diaphragm blood flow with contrast-enhanced ultrasound in healthy humans: feasibility, validity, and reliability* Doctoral dissertation, University of British Columbia, England. 120p.
- Cardillo, J.H., Zersen, K.M., & Cavanagh, A.A. (2024). Point of care ultrasound measurement of paralumbar caudal vena cava diameter and caudal vena cava to aortic ratio in hypovolemic dogs. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 11, 1467043.
- Chinh, N.D., Ha, L.M., Sun, G., Anh, L.Q., Huong, P.V., Vu, T.A., Trung, N.L. (2021). Short time cardiovascular pulses estimation for dengue fever screening via continuous-wave Doppler radar using empirical mode decomposition and continuous wavelet transform. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, 65, 102361.
- Chou, Y.Y., Ward, J.L., Barron, L.Z., Murphy, S.D., Tropf, M.A., Lisciandro, G.R., & DeFrancesco, T.C. (2021). Focused ultrasound of the caudal vena cava in dogs with cavitory effusions or congestive heart failure: a prospective, observational study. *PLoS One*, 16(5), e0252544.
- D'Anjou M.A, Penninck D, Cornejo L, Pibarto P. (2004). Ultrasonographic diagnosis of portosystemic shunting in dogs and cat. *Vet Radiol Ultrasound*; 45:424-437.
- Darnis, E., Boysen, S., Merveille, A.C., Desquilbet, L., Chalhoub, S., & Gommeren, K. (2018). Establishment of reference values of the caudal vena cava by fast-ultrasonography through different views in healthy dogs. *Journal of Veterinary Internal Medicine*, 32(4), 1308-1318.
- Derré, M., & Layssol-Lamour, C. (2022). Ultrasonographic characteristics of the portal venous system of 37 healthy, unsedated, student-owned cats: A prospective study. *The Canadian Veterinary Journal*, 63(4), 373.

- Dominique P, Marc-André D. (2008). *Atlas of small animal ultrasonography*, 2nd ed., 704p. Wiley-Blackwell Publishers Ames, USA.
- Ercolin, A.C M., Uchôa, A.S., Aires, L.P.N., Gomes, D R., Tinto, S.T., Feliciano, G.S.M., & Feliciano, M. A.R. (2024). Use of new ultrasonography methods for detecting neoplasms in dogs and cats: a review. *Animals*, *14*(2), 312.
- Evangelista, G.C.L., Viana, A.G.D.A., Neves, M.M., & Reis, E.C.C. (2022). Resistivity and pulsatility indexes in feline kidney disease: a systematic review. *Veterinary Radiology & Ultrasound*, *63*(3), 306-318.
- Fiori, G., Fuiano, F., Scorza, A., Conforto, S., & Sciuto, S.A. (2021). Non-invasive methods for PWV measurement in blood vessel stiffness assessment. *IEEE Reviews in Biomedical Engineering*, *15*, 169-183.
- Gori, E., Pierini, A., Lippi, I., Citi, S., Mannucci, T., & Marchetti, V. (2021). Evaluation of diagnostic and prognostic usefulness of abdominal ultrasonography in dogs with clinical signs of acute pancreatitis. *Journal of the American Veterinary Medical Association*, *259*(6), 631-636.
- Gupta, P., Bhardwaj, H.R., Gupta, A.K., Sharma, A., Nashiruddllah, N., & Kushwaha, R.B. (2022). Duplex doppler evaluation of distal intrarenal arteries in urinary tract diseases of dogs. *Indian Journal of Veterinary Surgery*, *43*(1), 46-49.
- Horsma, A. (2024). *Verification of Transverse Doppler-Ultrasound for Assessment of Blood Flow Velocity*. KTH Royal Institute of Technology, School of Engineering Sciences in Chemistry, Biotechnology and Health (CBH), *master thesis*. Stockholm, Sweden 91p.
- Ito, T., Hanazono, K., Miyoshi, K., & Endoh, D. (2024). Evaluation of renal function in dogs using pulsed Doppler ultrasonography. *Open Veterinary Journal*, *14*(12), 3449.
- Korim, F., Kuricová, M., & Eberlová, L. (2023). Anatomical Characteristics of Duplicated Caudal Vena Cava in Cats—A Case Report. *Animals*, *13*(10), 1585.
- Lamb C.R, Adrian B.O. (2005). Doppler ultrasound examination in dogs and cats. *Journal of In Practice*, *27*(4), 183-189.
- Maulik, D. (2023). Doppler sonography: a brief history. In *Doppler ultrasound in obstetrics and gynecology*, 3rd ed., 1-10p, Springer International Publishing Cham, Sweden.
- Meola, M., Ibeas, J., Lasalle, G., & Petrucci, I. (2021). Basics for performing a high-quality color Doppler sonography of the vascular access. *The Journal of Vascular Access*, *22*(1_suppl), 18-31.
- Meyers, B.A., & Vlachos, P.P. (2025). Flow measurements in clinical cardiac imaging. *Physical Review Fluids*, *10*(2), 020501.

- Miranda, E.D.P., & Carneiro, F. (2024). Principles of Doppler Ultrasound. In *Penile Color Duplex-Doppler Ultrasound in Erectile Dysfunction Diagnosis and Management: A Complete Guide to Best Practices*, 1st ed., 9-31p, Springer International Publishing, Cham, Sweden.
- Moarabi, A., Hanafi, M.G., Mosallanejad, B., & Alimardani, P. (2022). Measurement of normal renal artery indices in DSH cats by Doppler ultrasonography. *Iranian Veterinary Journal*, 17(4), 103-110.
- Novellas R, Gopegui RR, Espada Y. (2008). Increased renal vascular resistance in dogs with hepatic disease *The Veterinary Journal* 178, 255-260.
- Oglat, A.A. (2022). A review of blood-mimicking fluid properties using Doppler ultrasound applications. *Journal of Medical Ultrasound*, 30(4), 251-256.
- Percival, A., Slaughter, S., & Scrivani, P.V. (2025). Normative Canine Liver Ultrasonography: Papillary Process and Ligamentum Venosum Fissure. *Veterinary Radiology & Ultrasound*, 66(2), e70018.
- Samir, H., Radwan, F., & Watanabe, G. (2021). Advances in applications of color Doppler ultrasonography in the andrological assessment of domestic animals: A review. *Theriogenology*, 161, 252-261.
- Scheinfeld M.H, Bilali A, Koenigsberg M. (2009). Understanding the spectral Doppler waveform of the hepatic veins in health and disease. *Radiographics*, 29,2081-2098.
- Sharif, H.A., Mhalhal, T.R., & Ali, M.A. (2025). Comparative Morphological Study of the Kidney in the Domestic Dogs and Cats. *Basrah Journal of Veterinary Research*, 24(1), 164-178.
- Silva, V.B.C., Froes, T.R., Wolf, M., Lucina, S.B., & Sousa, M.G. (2022). Characterization of Doppler spectrum of hepatic veins in dogs with pulmonary hypertension. *Research in Veterinary Science*, 150, 131-136.
- Singh, A., Kusunose, J., Phipps, M.A., Wang, F., Chen, L.M., & Caskey, C.F. (2022). Guiding and monitoring focused ultrasound mediated blood–brain barrier opening in rats using power Doppler imaging and passive acoustic mapping. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 14758.
- Stillman, Z.R., Ruvolo, D.J., Fettig, P.K., & Carberry, C.A. (2025). Primary splenic torsion and subsequent avulsion in an English bulldog (*Canis lupus familiaris*). *Veterinary Record Case Reports*, 13(2), e70060.
- Tollefson, C. (2021). *The effects of sildenafil on portal vein velocity, cross-sectional area, and congestion index in the dog*. Master Thesis, Mississippi State University. Mississippi, USA. 36p.
- Udeh, C., Omer, T., & Zahniser, M.H. (2024). Doppler. In *Critical Care Echocardiography: A Self-Assessment Book*, 1st ed., 7-22p. Springer International Publishing, Cham, Sweden.

von Stade, L., & Marolf, A.J. (2022). Advanced Imaging of the Pancreas. *Advances in Small Animal Care*, 3(1), 57-71.

Yan, S., Shou, J., Yu, J., Song, J., Mao, Y., & Xu, K. (2023). Ultrafast ultrasound vector Doppler for small vasculature imaging. *IEEE Transactions on Ultrasonics, Ferroelectrics, and Frequency Control*, 70(7), 613-624.

